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P-Q Relationships and Sequences

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P-Q Relationships and Sequences

Let $A = \{a_n\}, n \geq 1$ be a sequence of numbers and q, p integers ≥ 1 .

We say that the terms $a_{k+1}, a_{k+2}, \dots, a_{k+p}, a_{k+p+1}, a_{k+p+2}, \dots, a_{k+p+q}$ satisfy a $p - q$ relationship if

$$a_{k+1} \diamond a_{k+2} \diamond \dots \diamond a_{k+p} = a_{k+p+1} \diamond a_{k+p+2} \diamond \dots \diamond a_{k+p+q}$$

where $\diamond$ may be any arithmetic operation, although it is generally a binary relation on A . If this relationship is satisfied for any $k \geq 1$, then $\{a_n\}, n \geq 1$ is said to be a $p - q - \diamond$ sequence. For operations such as addition, where $\diamond = +$, the sequence is called a $p - q$ -additive sequence.

As a specific case, we can easily see that the Fibonacci/Lucas sequence ($a_n + a_{n+1} = a_{n+2}$, for $n \geq 1$), is a $3 - 1$ -additive sequence.

Definition. Given any integer $n \geq 1$, the value of the Smarandache function $S(n)$ is the smallest integer m such that n divides $m!$.

If we consider the sequence of numbers that are the values of the Smarandache function for the integers $n \geq 1$,

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 7, 4, 6, 5, 11, 4, 13, 7, 5, 6, 17, ...

they can be incorporated into questions involving the $p - q - \diamond$ relationships.

a) How many ordered quadruples are there of the form $(S(n), S(n+1), S(n+2), S(n+3))$ such that $S(n+1) + S(n+2) = S(n+3) + S(n+4)$ which is a 2-2-additive relationship?

The three quadruples

$$S(6) + S(7) = S(8) + S(9), \quad 3 + 7 = 4 + 6;$$

$$S(7) + S(8) = S(9) + S(10), \quad 7 + 4 = 6 + 5;$$

$$S(28) + S(29) = S(30) + S(31), \quad 7 + 29 = 5 + 31.$$

are known. Are there any others? At this time, these are the only known solutions.

b) How many quadruples satisfy the 2-2-subtrac relationship $S(n+1) - S(n+2) = S(n+3) - S(n+4)$?

The three quadruples

$$S(1) - S(2) = S(3) - S(4), \quad 1 - 2 = 3 - 4;$$

$$S(2) - S(3) = S(4) - S(5), \quad 2 - 3 = 4 - 5;$$

$$S(49) - S(50) = S(51) - S(52), \quad 14 - 10 = 17 - 13$$

are known. Are there any others?

c) How many 6-tuples satisfy the 2-3-additive relationship $S(n+1) + S(n+2) + S(n+3) = S(n+4) + S(n+5) + S(n+6)$?

The only known solution is

$$S(5) + S(6) + S(7) = S(8) + S(9) + S(10), \quad 5 + 3 + 7 = 4 + 6 + 5.$$

Charles Ashbacher has a computer program that calculates the values of the Smarandache function. Therefore, he may be able to find additional solutions to these problems.

More general, if f_p is a p -ary raltion and g_q a q -ary relation, both defined on the set $\{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots\}$, then $a_{i_1}, a_{i_2}, \dots, a_{i_p}, a_{j_1}, a_{j_2}, \dots, a_{j_q}$ satisfies a $f_p - g_q$ relationship if

$$f(a_{i_1}, a_{i_2}, \dots, a_{i_p}) = g(a_{j_1}, a_{j_2}, \dots, a_{j_q}).$$

If this relationship holds for all terms of the sequence, then $\{a_n\}, n \geq 1$ is called a $f_p - g_q$ sequence.

Study some $f_p - g_q$ relationship for well-known sequences, such as the perfect numbers, Ulam numbers, abundant numbers, Catalan numbers and Cullen numbers. For example, a 2-2-additive, subtractive or multiplicative relationship.